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Academic Supervision and Professional Performance of State High School Teachers

Indra Prasetya¹

¹ Postgraduate, Muhammadiyah University of North Sumatra, Medan, Indonesia

Correspondence: Indra Prasetya, Postgraduate, Muhammadiyah University of North Sumatra, Medan, Indonesia, 20371, Tel (061) 88811104. E-mail: indraprasetya@umsu.ac.id

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to describe the implementation of academic supervision and best practices in the implementation of academic supervision in Public High School, Sumatera Utara Province, Indonesia. Academic supervision is a set of activities designed to help teachers develop their ability to manage the learning process in the classroom. The results of this study indicate that in order to implement effective supervision, the supervisor must be able to choose the best practice to be applied. The academic supervision techniques implemented are individual supervision techniques and group supervision techniques. The individual supervision techniques implemented are: 1) classroom visits, 2) classroom observations, 3) individual meetings, 4) inter-classroom visits and 5) self-assessment. Group techniques are implemented by involving a number of teachers in solving problems, talking and discussing together with the supervisors. The implementation of academic supervision at Public High School, includes (1) the planning stage with activities to prepare a schedule for the implementation of supervision, an evaluation program, a follow-up program for the results of the evaluation of supervision, the preparation of administrative documents, (2) the implementation stage, (3) the evaluation stage of the results of supervision, (4) the follow-up stage.

Keywords: Academic Supervision, Best Practices, Teacher Professional Performance

1. Introduction

The body of a manuscript opens with an introduction that presents the specific problem under study and describes the research strategy. Because the introduction is clearly identified by its position in the manuscript, it does not carry a heading labeling it the introduction. Before writing the introduction, consider the following questions (Person & Brew, 2002): Teachers are the dominant factor in improving the quality of education (Aqib & Elham, 2007). Through a quality learning process in the form of planning, implementation and evaluation so that it is effective and efficient (Fritz & Miller, 2003). Therefore, students experience an increase in knowledge, skills, attitudes, motivation, talent, interest, personality, intelligence and noble character because the authority and responsibility of teachers is to educate, guide, instruct, train, assess and evaluate students so that the participants themselves have the optimal quality of knowledge based on the potential of the knowledge they possess (Glickman., Gordon & Ross-Gordon, 2007).

For this reason, teachers, as an important part of the organisation of education, must be able to work professionally. Professional in the sense that teacher must have special skills and work according to the knowledge they have mastered in order to make a positive contribution to improving the quality of education (Tyagi, 2018). Professional teachers have personal, social, intellectual, moral and spiritual responsibilities that are in line with their main duties and functions to educate, teach, guide, direct, train, assess and evaluate students by making them partners in learning, because their hope is to become moral, creative and innovative people to achieve their goals (Alila, Uusiautti, & Matta, 2016).

Generally, there are three tasks of the teacher as a profession, such as to educate, teach and train (Silva & Dana, 2001). On the other hand, teacher's duties can also change behaviour and discipline to guide students towards the desired goal and prepare generations of people who can live and play an active role in society (Abas, 2019). Teacher professionalism in educational activities can produce students who are truly qualified in both academic, non-academic, ethical, moral, attitude, behaviour, character and others because teachers have the right knowledge, skills and values (Sullivan & Glanz, 2005). In the implementation of teacher professionalism, it can be carried out through the learning process in the classroom, by creating a climate and services for the abilities, potentials, interests, talents and needs of different learners, so that there is an optimal interaction between teachers and students and between students and students (Suhertian, 2010; Sagala, 2010), so that a professional learning process takes place (Prasetia., Akrim & Sulasmi, 2022).

In order to professionally optimise learning activities, teachers must have good intellectual abilities, understand the vision and mission of national education, have the expertise to effectively transfer knowledge to students, understand the concept of psychological development of children, have the ability to organise the learning process, and have creativity and the art of teaching (Bright, 2019). In addition, they also have the expertise or ability to guide and nurture students both intellectually, spiritually and emotionally (Sullivan & Glanz, 2005).

Poor teacher competence will certainly have a negative impact on the quality of education in schools and, more specifically, on the quality of students' human resources. Therefore, concrete steps to improve teacher competence are needed to make a positive contribution to enhance teacher performance (Alan, 2021). Improving teacher performance can be done by providing better welfare, training, supervision and performance evaluation, shaping the mentality of teachers, tightening the recruitment process and increasing the use of technology (Kahramanoglu, 2019).

Teacher performance is defined as the achievements, results, and abilities achieved or demonstrated by teachers in carrying out their educational and teaching tasks (Lorensius, Anggal & Lugas, 2022) and the performance of teachers in carrying out their duties as educators (Fall & Sutton, 2004). According to Sagala (2010) the performance of teachers is not optimal. Teachers only perform their duties as routine activities. Teachers should be able to Innovate learning. Instead, learning innovation for teachers is relatively constrained and creativity is not considered part of performance. The poor performance of teachers is due to low salaries and incentives or income levels, competence, work discipline, job satisfaction, the organization where teachers teach, principal leadership, government policies on education, supervision services and the application of supervision that has not been maximised (Suhertian, 2010).

In particular, supervision activities can basically have a positive impact on improving teacher performance. This is because supervision activities on teacher performance are a form of planned activities to assist teachers in doing their jobs effectively, which improves teachers' performance in carrying out their professional duties (Lorensius, Silpanus & Ping, 2021). Supervision is basically a service and assistance, improvement, guidance to teachers in improving teaching and learning activities in accordance with their professional duties. Comprehensively, it aims to support, guide and assess the ability of teachers in education and teaching based on their respective fields to make the necessary improvements by working together and looking for problems that teachers experience in the learning process and then find a way out to overcome these problems, which in the end the learning process can be conducted (Marmoah, 2018).

In supervision activities to improve teaching and learning, it is often emphasised in educational supervision activities because the scope of activities relates to the technical teaching and learning carried out by teachers, students, principals and school supervisors. Supervision or educational supervision in essence is the efforts of supervisors in providing services to educational stakeholders, especially teachers, both individually and in groups, in an attempt to promote and improve the quality of learning processes and outcomes (Sahertian, 2010). The support provided by supervisors can make a positive contribution to teachers and can proceed well if there is a unified perception, commitment, openness, supervision and coaching planning prepared jointly by supervisors and teachers, sharing of responsibilities between supervisors and teachers and building harmonious relationships between supervisors and teachers (Glickman, Gordon & Gordon, 2007).

Educational supervision activities are very important to implement because it can improve teachers' professionalism in terms of quality and teachers' performance in teaching and learning activities in the classroom, so that it contributes positively and directly to improving the quality of learners (students). Thus, the purpose of educational supervision is basically to support teachers in the development and implementation of the curriculum in the teaching and learning process, to improve the potential quality of teachers in classroom teaching and to develop school staff, so that ultimately it will improve the quality of student learning (Silva & Dana, 2001).

Supervision activities are generally divided into three forms, such as academic, managerial and institutional supervision. Academic supervision emphasises the supervisor's observations on academic issues related to the learning and teaching process. Managerial supervision focuses the supervisor's observations on administrative aspects to facilitate the implementation of learning. Institutional supervision highlights the supervisor's observations on the institutional aspects of the school, especially the school's performance (Mensah, 2019).

Specifically, academic supervision is the ability of the supervisor to carry out academic supervision, that is, to evaluate and develop teachers to improve the quality of the learning process carried out, including the subject matter of learning, the preparation of syllabus and lesson plans, the selection of strategies/methods/techniques, the use of media and information technology, the evaluation of the process and results, and classroom action research, so as to have a positive impact on the quality of student learning outcomes (McGhee & Stark, 2018). The basic essence of academic supervision in the effort to improve the quality of teaching and learning by teachers in order to improve the quality of student knowledge, certainly has a positive aim to improve learning activities in an educational institution (school). Sagala (2010) the purpose of academic supervision is basically to help teachers improve their skills to become better and professional teachers in the implementation of teaching. On the other hand, Mehr., Ladany & Caskie (2010) suggests that the purpose of academic supervision is to help teachers develop their abilities, develop curriculum, develop teacher working groups and guide teachers in classroom action research.

Based on the above, this study was conducted to improve teachers' professional performance through supervision activities by school principals and to create best practices in supervision activities for teachers in Public High School's Province of North Sumatra, Indonesia.

2. Method

This research is a school action research conducted by the principal. The focus of the research is clinical supervision on academic aspects, which is the learning process organised by teachers at Public High School in 5 schools spread across the Province of North Sumatra, Indonesia. The description of the research participant is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Overview of the Research Participant

School Name	Participant Gender (N)		N
	Male	Female	
Public High School 1	6	6	12
Public High School 2	7	5	13

Public High School 3	5	6	11
Public High School 11	7	5	12
Public High School 15	9	7	16
Amount	34	29	54

The action procedures carried out included planning, alternative solutions to problems, and preparing the various data collection instruments needed. Afterwards, the action was carried out according to the plan determined in the planning section (Praseti, 2022). When the action was carried out, it was also observed using the tools prepared during the planning. After the observation of the action, a reflection was carried out, which was a discussion between the actors of the action (teachers and principals) to evaluate the next action. Data collection techniques were through interviews, observation and documentation. Material or media used as another tool in data collection was a recording device (video). Data analysis techniques were data reduction, data presentation, conclusion drawing/verification, which was an interactive cycle (Miles & Huberman, 2014).

3. Results

The implementation and results of the research in the field are described in the data description. The most important stage in the implementation of supervision in schools is planning, implementation, evaluation and follow-up. This stage analyses how supervision can be carried out more effectively and efficiently in order to achieve better educational goals. This stage of the study will produce best practice supervision that can ultimately be used to improve teachers' professional performance.

To obtain information on how supervision is implemented in Public High School, the data analysis technique used in the field research was through descriptive analysis, which was conducted repeatedly. While data collection techniques used questionnaires, interviews, observation and documentation studies. The respondents at this stage were 54 subject teachers. While the indicators used were such as the planning, implementation, evaluation and follow-up stages of academic supervision. In the implementation of academic supervision in the field, it used individual and group supervision techniques.

3.1. Supervisory Planning Practice

In supervision activities, the planning stage is very necessary, whether in individual or group supervision. Planning is a pre-supervision activity carried out by the supervisor (principal) together with the teacher, which is an initial review activity, a data collection activity or an initial review of problems before carrying out supervision activities. A well-planned supervision makes it easier for the supervisor to carry out the supervision in a way that minimises errors. In the area of supervision planning, the researchers conducted interviews with teachers to obtain information about the importance of planning in supervision activities.

“Structured and systematic planning is the main prerequisite for the success of the supervision to be carried out. This is because planning is basically a guide that can be used to carry out activities in order to achieve the goals to be achieved” (Teacher interview, P-1).

In the implementation of supervision in schools, the planning stage is an important part that needs to be carried out by supervisors. This is in line with what one of the teachers stated:

“Planning is an important aspect of conducting a supervision, especially for us teachers who need help in solving teaching problems in the classroom. Because at this stage the supervisor will prepare various things that are needed before carrying out the supervision” (Teacher Interview, P-3).

“Other interviewees also argued that the success of academic supervision activities carried out by school principals for us is highly dependent on the maturity of the planning carried out” (Teacher Interview, P-4).

The two opinions above show that planning activities are an important part of carrying out supervision. Since supervision is different from inspection, planning is expected to be a guideline in providing guidance to teachers to improve the teaching and learning process in the classroom. Effective teaching requires a variety of strategies.

In order to achieve this goal, an effective system of supervision must be in place. Effective supervision is highly dependent on effective planning.

In connection with the implementation of academic supervision at Public High School, one of the activities carried out in the planning stage is the preparation of supervision planning documents and monitoring documents by principals together with teachers. The planning documents prepared include (1) documents of teachers' learning materials to be supervised, (2) annual, monthly and weekly activities, (3) schedules of class visits, and (4) documents of evaluation instruments for the implementation of supervision. This is in line with what was stated by the teachers who mentioned that "there must be a plan prepared collaboratively between the principal and the teacher for each implementation of supervision in the classroom. Similarly, 'at this stage there needs to be a common understanding of the concept, benefits, objectives and its application.

3.2. Supervision Implementation Practices

In practice, supervision at Public High School is effective. This is because before carrying out supervision activities, planning is carried out together with the teachers according to the problems and needs of the teachers in the field. Supervision planning activities are important in carrying out supervision. This is because in this activity the supervisor (principal) can identify all the problems faced by the teachers and work together to identify solutions to solve these problems. This aspect of collaboration and participation effectively builds a conducive atmosphere and climate, a feeling of comfort and familiarity between the principal as supervisor and the teachers. Building positive relationships in the implementation of supervision is the best practice in supervision activities. This is in line with what the teachers said:

“We feel comfortable and happy in the implementation of supervision by the principal because we feel involved in the supervision process. We also identify problems and solutions and set the schedule for class visits together. When supervision is carried out, the principal and the teachers do not see a barrier between the supervisor and the supervisee, because a collegial, participative and empowering relationship has been established between us” (Teacher interview, P-31).

In the implementation of supervision at Public High School, the activities carried out by the supervisor include four activities carried out by the principal at this stage of implementing academic supervision, which are: (1) supervising learning tools, (2) supervising the monitoring of lesson plans, (3) supervising the learning process, and (4) supervising the assessment of student learning outcomes. This activity basically takes place when the teacher is learning in the classroom and the supervisor (principal) makes observations and various other actions, especially in the supervision process during the teacher's teaching and learning process in the classroom.

For the implementation of supervision to be effective, the supervisor (principal) must have the right way of carrying out supervision, both in supervising learning tools, in implementing learning and in evaluating learning. The difference in the number of teachers to be supervised determines the level of effectiveness. In schools with a small number of teachers, supervision activities can be carried out individually, but in schools with a large number of teachers, supervision can be carried out in groups. Specifically, in the implementation of supervision of the learning process, supervision activities at Public High School are carried out using individual or individual techniques arranged based on each teacher's class schedule. In the implementation of supervision in this class, the teacher's teaching activities in the classroom or the implementation of supervision through recording techniques (documented) uses digital video recording devices. The presence of the supervisor in the classroom does not have to be 100% present. The supervisor's activity in the classroom is only to ensure that any matters or technicalities relating to any support facilities, such as recording equipment, are properly available and can be operated. This means that during the observation phase, the supervisor will not enter the classroom directly, but will do so via video recording.

The use of technology or media in human life activities is actually very beneficial, especially for the implementation of academic supervision at Public High School. Supervision of learning in the classroom with the help of this recording media in practice is very effective and efficient, which is able to produce a process of supervision activities that is free from the burden, depressed atmosphere and discomfort of the teachers in the

classroom. This is because the teachers do not feel disturbed and are very confident with the supervision model supported by these recording media. As the teachers have an opinion about the implementation of the supervision carried out with this video recording technique, including:

“The implementation of supervision using this recording technique is, in our opinion, very helpful, practical and enjoyable, away from the feeling of pressure and loss of self-confidence. We can see the results of the recording of learning implementation, assess and analilise aspects of our weaknesses and strengths repeatedly in learning practice... obviously this is very practical, effective and efficient in supervision activities”. (Teacher Interview, P7).

It can be explained that the best practice in implementing learning supervision in the classroom can be carried out by recording teachers' teaching activities in the classroom by using media or recording devices. The advantages of supervision through this recording activity are that (1) the recording can be stored for a long time, (2) it can be repeated, and (3) it becomes material for improving the professional performance of the teacher.

3.3. Evaluation Practice and Supervision Report

In this stage of evaluation, the activity carried out is to reflect on teacher learning activities in the classroom. The evaluation of the teacher's learning is, obviously, carried out through the data of the video recording. This evaluation activity is carried out by the supervisor (principal) together with the teacher by evaluating the recording of the teacher's teaching activities in the classroom. The activity of evaluating or analysing this video recording can be divided into two analyses, (1) the analysis is carried out individually (evaluation by principal or teacher) and (2) the analysis is carried out collaboratively (principal and teacher).

Individual analysis. In an individual analysis, the school manager evaluates video recordings of teacher learning activities in the classroom. The principal records and evaluates all teacher learning activities on the basis of the evaluation tool and then prepares an evaluation report. The assessment report on teacher learning in the classroom must be given to each teacher and then discussed with the teacher for the next follow-up. In the case of individual analysis by teachers, if teachers have been authorised by the principal to carry out self-assessment and objectively evaluate themselves on the basis of the assessment instruments prepared, then they submit a report on the results of their assessment to the principal and together they discuss, identify solutions and plan corrective or follow-up actions.

Collaborative analysis. Effective evaluation is carried out collaboratively by principals and teachers or through peer involvement. Principals and teachers carry out collaborative assessments and produce reports on all teacher learning activities in the classroom through videotaped learning. They identify strengths and weaknesses together, and work together to find and follow up solutions.

Implementation of supervision has a positive effect on improving teacher professional performance. During the implementation process up to the evaluation, the participants have shown good performance during class teaching. Total of 34 participants showed very good performance (62.96%), 6 participants with good performance (29.63%), 11 participants with pretty good performance (25.93%). Teacher performance is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Participant Profesional Performance

Score Interval	Category	F	%
90 – 100	very good	34	62,96
80 – 89	good	16	29,63
70 – 79	Enough	14	25,93
< 70	Need guidance	0	0,00
Total		54	100

The results of the supervision evaluation based on the participants' assessment provide an explanation as in Table 2.

Table 2: Participant Assessment of Supervision Practice

No	Rated Aspect	Partisipant Perception
1	Clarity of supervision objective	Very good
2	The relevance of supervision to teacher needs	Good
3	Supervision planning	Very good
4	Implementation of supervision	Very good
5	Teacher participation in supervision	Very high
6	Contextual Supervision	Very precise
7	Supervision builds harmonius	Very high
8	Supervision effectiveness	Very effective

Based on Table 1 above, the participants rated the practice of supervision as effective and as expected, based on 8 perceived indicators. This means that the supervision practices carried out can become models of academic supervision that need to be imitated and implemented.

Based on the supervision practices that have been implemented at Public High School, there is a general improvement in teacher performance compared to previous performance. The academic supervision model developed as an effort to improve teachers' professional performance at Public High School consists of four stages, which are (1) supervision planning; (2) supervision implementation; (3) supervision evaluation and follow-up; (4) reporting results. The four stages are shown in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Factual Practices of Academic Supervision

Supervision activities are the main tasks and functions of school principals or supervisors. It aims to improve learning activities and the improvement and professional development of teachers. Ideally, efforts to improve learning activities should come from teachers themselves, not from principals or supervisors.

This is the view of experts on academic supervision that is, coaching teachers' performance in managing learning (Sullivan & Glanz, 2005). According to Knox et al. (2008) the activity of promoting teacher performance in managing the teaching and learning process. Clinical supervision is the activity of coaching teachers to improve performance in the learning process. According to Fall & Sutton (2004) there are two aims of clinical supervision: (1) professional development, and (2) motivating teachers' work and improving ineffective learning processes. Supervision is a planned coaching activity to assist teachers and other school staff to perform their jobs effectively (Goodwin, Roegman & Reagan, 2016). Supervision is an integral part of the whole process of educational administration, which is primarily aimed at developing the effectiveness of the performance of school personnel in relation to the main tasks of education. Supervision is the effort of school officials in guiding

teachers and other officials in improving teaching, including stimulating, selecting the growth and development of teachers and revising educational goals, teaching materials and methods and teaching evaluation (Suhertian, 2010). This is supported by the results of Triani's research (2008) in the initial study of the principal's understanding of clinical supervision was not good, after the research developed to be very good and was able to carry out clinical supervision appropriately, so that difficulties in the use of basic teaching skills could be improved.

4. Conclusion

The implementation of supervision at Public High School has produced best practices that have an impact on improving teachers' professional performance. The supervision practices include aspects of planning, implementation, evaluation and follow-up and reporting. In the planning stage, what is carried out is the compilation of supervision planning documents and monitoring documents by the principal and teachers. The planning documents compiled include (1) documents of the teachers' learning materials to be supervised, (2) annual, monthly and weekly activities, (3) schedules of class visits, and (4) documents of evaluation instruments for the implementation of supervision. Specifically, in the implementation of learning supervision, supervision activities at Public High School are carried out with individual techniques through learning video recording techniques. The use of technology or media in the implementation of academic supervision at Public High School is very effective and efficient, which is able to produce a process of supervision activities that are free from the burden, depressed atmosphere and discomfort of teachers in the classroom. This is because teachers do not feel disturbed and are very confident with the technology-assisted supervision model. Meanwhile, evaluation activities were carried out through the analysis of video recordings of teachers' classroom teaching activities. Analyses of the video recordings of teaching activities were carried out on the basis of: (1) individual analyses (assessments by principals or teachers independently), and (2) collaborative analyses (principals together with teachers). The results of the evaluation of the implementation of supervision are then reported to the responsible parties (principals and teachers) for follow-up. Based on the practice of supervision carried out at Public High School, it generally leads to better teacher performance compared to previous performance.

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